

Assessment of Machine Learning Models in Characterization of Magnetodielectric Composites

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With the current advancements in additive manufacturing and 3D printing, magnetodielectric (MD) composites have become increasingly interesting for developing applications in the microwave range. To characterize these materials, approaches that combine the use of machine learning (ML) models with well-established microwave characterization techniques, such as split ring resonators (SRRs), are increasingly employed for the electromagnetic determination of complex permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ) [1]. In this regard, this study evaluates several well-known ML models and determines their applicability to the simultaneous determination of both permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ). Particularly, this work delves into the methodological considerations affecting the reliability of ML models evaluation, systematically assessing several relevant models for regression problems in the field of microwave characterization [2]: linear regression, support vector machines, random forest, and artificial neural networks. Based on the analysis of performance metrics such as mean squared error (MSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2), the model with the greatest generalization capability is determined. Furthermore, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [3] is applied as an explainability technique to quantify the influence of each input feature on the simultaneous prediction of ϵ and μ . The results show that the model with the best generalization capability and robustness was the linear regression with second-degree polynomial features. The model explains over 99% of the variance in ϵ and μ as a function of the frequency response, with an error of 0.0014. SHAP values have indicated that the magnitude of the reflection coefficient and dielectric losses are decisive in predicting ϵ and μ . These results support the application of the ML-guided approach for characterization of magnetodielectric composites.

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